

AHARA VIDHI VIDHAN: A FORGOTTEN FRAMEWORK FOR FUTURE NUTRITIONAL SCIENCE

¹*Dr. Disha J. Soriya, ²Dr. Amisha L. Dabhi, ³Dr. Maulik B. Patel,
⁴Prof. Dr. Aniket A. Shilwant, ⁵Prof. Dr. Sarita S. Bhutada

¹Assistant Professor Department of Kriya Sharira GJPIASR, Anand.

²Assistant Professor Department of Samhita Siddhanta and Sanskrit GJPIASR, Anand.

³Assistant Professor Department of Rachana Sharira Bhargva Anand.

⁴Professor and HOD Department of Kriya Sharira GJPIASR, Anand.

⁵Professor and Principal Department of Kriya Sharira GJPIASR, Anand.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Disha J. Soriya

Assistant Professor Department of
Kriya Sharira GJPIASR, Anand.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Ahara, or diet, is regarded by Ayurveda as the primary pillar of life (Trayopasthambha). Ahara Vidhi is described in depth in the classical Samahita, highlighting the importance of food in health, disease prevention, and therapy. These ideas align with modern views of lifestyle medicine, nutrients, and dietetics. **Methods:** A thorough literature review was carried out using classical Ayurvedic books, along with their respective commentaries. Additionally, contemporary scientific publications. Relevant studies and review articles addressing Ahara Vidhi, food classification, digestive processes, dietary regimens, and their physiological effects were included in the review. **Results:** The findings reveal that the Samhitas present a comprehensive and multidimensional understanding of food. This includes: (i) Ahara Vidhi Vidhan (ii) classification of food based such as guna, rasa, virya, and

vipaka, (iii) the concept of Pathya–Apathya (iv) seasonal and individualized dietary recommendations, and (v) the therapeutic application of food in disease prevention.

Contemporary scientific research substantiates these traditional principles, linking them with modern concepts such as nutritional science, gut microbiome regulation and functional foods.

Discussion: Ayurvedic principles show strong correspondence with contemporary

approaches in preventive nutrition and precision dietetics. Incorporating the concept of Ahara Vidhi into modern dietary practice may offer innovative perspectives for advancing personalized nutrition strategies.

KEYWORDS: Ahara Vidhi, Ayurveda, dietetics, nutrition.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, The Science of Life

Charaka Samhita and other Ayurvedic classics explain that health depends not only on what we eat, but also on how we eat. In Ayurveda, Ahara (food) is considered one of the three important pillars of life along with Nidra (sleep) and Brahmacharya (disciplined lifestyle). Charaka Samhita explains that food is the basic support of life. The growth, nourishment, strength, immunity, and longevity of a person depend upon proper Ahara. In Ayurveda, food is viewed as both medicine and nourishment. Therefore, proper diet is called **Mahabhaishajya** (greatest medicine). Ayurveda emphasizes that health depends not only on the type of food consumed but also on the method of eating. Digestion, absorption, and metabolism are influenced by physical, mental, emotional, and environmental factors. For this reason, the Ayurvedic Acharyas described specific dietary rules called **Ahara Vidhi Vidhan**.

These rules explain:

- What to eat
- How much to eat
- When to eat
- How to eat
- Which combinations should be avoided
- How digestion should be protected

In ancient times people were conscious about healthy eating and food quality. However, in modern society people are more attracted toward processed foods, excessive spicy food, junk food, reheated food, irregular timing, and overeating. Busy schedules and mental stress further disturb digestion and metabolism. As a result, lifestyle disorders are rapidly increasing worldwide. Ayurvedic dietary principles therefore remain highly relevant in modern times.

Importance of Ahara in Ayurveda

Ayurveda states that the body and mind are formed from food. Proper Ahara supports:

- Bala (strength)
- Varna (healthy complexion)
- Ojas (immunity and vitality)
- Ayushya (longevity)
- Mental satisfaction
- Proper tissue nourishment
- Disease resistance

Improper food habits become the cause of disease formation. Therefore, Ayurveda places great importance on daily dietary discipline.

Modern medical science also confirms that unhealthy dietary habits contribute to:

- Diabetes mellitus
- Obesity
- Cardiovascular diseases
- Gastrointestinal disorders
- Mental stress and depression

This idea provides basic guidelines for food preparation, quantity, timing, and method of consumption. Because they concentrate on digestion, metabolism, mental health, and illness prevention, these concepts are quite helpful even in contemporary nutritional research.

Modern life style and dietary problem

In this modern era - people are trying to live luxurious life. Always disturbed physically and mentally because of highly competitive society. people are so involved in them that they are least conscious about their - aahara, nidra and brahmcharya. Food habits - excessive intake, high protein diet, spicy, oily, harmful combination together, taking food without analysing agnibala are leading causes for diseases. So, Aahar vidhi vidhan which is useful for humankind because after all health is the pavement step to achieve aims of human life.

Thus, both Ayurveda and modern nutrition agree that food plays a major role in maintaining health.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate and prepare data regarding various dietary rules (Ahara Vidhi Vidhana) mentioned in Ayurvedic texts, along with their design and utility under the purview of Charaka Samhita.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sources of data: classical ayurvedic texts—Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita etc.

Databases searched: PubMed, Scopus, web of science, google scholar, Ayush research portal etc.

Search strategy: "ahara vidhi," "ayurveda nutrition," "food and health ayurveda," "pathya-apathya," and Ahara classification were among the keywords used.

Main Principles of Ahara Vidhi Vidhan (Dietary Rules)

1. Ushna Ahara – Eat Warm and Fresh Food

Ayurveda recommends consuming warm and freshly prepared food. Warm food stimulates digestive fire (Agni), improves digestion, enhances taste, and supports proper movement of Vata. Warm food also helps in reducing increased Kapha.

Cold, stale, preserved, and reheated foods reduce digestive power and may lead to indigestion, bloating, heaviness, and toxin formation.

Modern nutrition also supports fresh food because highly processed and reheated foods may lose nutrients and produce harmful compounds.

2. Snigdha Ahara – Food should be unctuous

Food should contain moderate unctuousness such as ghee and healthy oils. Snigdha Ahara improves digestion, complexion, nourishment, it gets digested quickly, it helps in downward movement of Vata, and strength.

Ayurveda discourages excessive dry, hard, roasted, and processed foods because they disturb Vata and reduce tissue nourishment.

Fats and oils provide a concentrated source of energy and the essential fatty acids are needed for growth and health. They aid for the absorption of some vitamins such as vitamin and improve the taste of meals. Different fat nutrients are found in fats and oil. Unsaturated fatty acids are among them. cholesterol, trans fats, and saturated fats. Every cell in our body has a unique membrane that is primarily made of fat. Organs including the brain and nerves are largely composed of fat. Fat makes a great fuel.

Modern science explains that healthy fats are important for.

- Brain function
- Hormone synthesis
- Cell membrane structure
- Vitamin absorption
- Energy production

However, repeated reheating of oils and excessive trans fats are harmful to health.

3. Matratvat Ahara – Proper Quantity of Food

Food should be taken in proper quantity according to digestive capacity.

Overeating may lead to Obesity, Indigestion, Ama formation, Diabetes, Metabolic disorders and Under-eating may lead to weakness, fatigue, and nutritional deficiency.

Ayurveda advises leaving some space in the stomach for proper digestion and movement of doshas. This principle resembles modern concepts of calorie balance and portion control.

Food consumed in proper quantity keeps Tridosha in normalcy, thereby increasing the lifespan of a person. Proper quantity does not impair the power of digestion and ensures proper peristalsis and comfortable passage of food toward the rectum after being properly digested before being expelled out. Chakrapani clears that food consumed in a proper quantity stays in its place and thus not disturb other Dosha. The quantity of food taken that gets digested in proper time without affecting the normalcy of the body is called as Matra or the measure of proper quantity. One should always eat either half or one third of the stomach and leave the rest for liquid and other bodily humors. Consuming food in less quantity results in all types of Vataroga; the depletion of strength, color of body, on the other hand, when taken in excess will cause instant Tridoshakopa and result in, Amapradosha (Diseases of ama), which may further lead to many other metabolic diseases.

4. Jirne Ashniyat – Eat After Digestion of Previous Meal

Ayurveda strongly advises taking food only after the previous meal has been properly digested.

Signs of proper digestion include.

- Natural hunger
- Feeling of lightness
- Proper belching

- Clear bowel movement
- Freshness of mind

Eating before digestion produces Ama , which becomes the root cause of disease.

Modern science also recognizes that poor meal timing and continuous eating disturb metabolism and insulin regulation.

5. Viruddhahara – Incompatible Food Combinations

Ayurveda explains that certain food combinations are harmful to the body. Examples include:

- Milk with fish
- Honey and ghee in equal quantity
- Reheated oils
- Excessively processed food combinations

Such combinations disturb digestion and may lead to Skin diseases and chronic diseases.

Modern food science also explains harmful effects of certain incompatible food reactions, allergens, and toxic compounds formed during reheating.

6. Eat in a Calm Environment

Ayurveda advises eating in a peaceful and comfortable place with proper attention. One should avoid eating while:

- Watching television
- Using mobile phones
- Talking excessively
- Laughing continuously
- Walking or standing

Digestion functions best when the mind is relaxed.

Modern research on mindful eating also shows that distraction during meals can increase overeating and poor digestion.

7. Avoid Eating Too Fast or Too Slow

Eating too quickly can lead to improper chewing, overeating, and poor digestion. Eating too slowly may cool the food and disturb digestive activity.

Proper chewing and moderate eating speed help better digestion and nutrient absorption.

8. Eat with Concentration (Tanmana Bhunjita)

Ayurveda explains that food should be eaten with full concentration and awareness. Emotional disturbances such as anger, stress, fear, and anxiety negatively affect digestion. Today emotional eating and stress-related digestive disorders are very common. This shows the importance of the Ayurvedic view regarding the mind-gut relationship.

Dwadasha Ashan Pravicharana.

Type of Anna	Indication
Sheet Ahara	Thirsty, alcoholic, burning, Raktapitta and emaciated individuals
Ushna Ahara	Kaphaja and Vataja disorders and after Virechan and Snehan (olation therapy)
Snigdha Ahara	Ruksha individuals and individuals with Vata prakriti in vataja disorders
Ruksha Ahara	Obese, people with diabetes and individuals with excess Kapha
Drava Ahara	Dehydrated and weak individuals
Shushka Ahara	Skin disorders, erysipelas and diabetes mellitus.
Ek Kalika Ahara	Individuals with mand Agni (digestive power)
DwiKalika Ahara	Proper Agni
AushadhaYuktAh ahara	Patients who are unable to take unpalatable drugs.
Matraheen Ahara	Individuals with impaired Agni and disease
Prashamaka Ahara	Advised according to seasonal variation
Vrutyartha Ahara	Advised in healthy individuals

Agni and Ama

Agni

Agni is responsible for digestion, absorption, metabolism, and tissue nourishment. Proper Agni maintains health while weak Agni causes disease.

Different types of Agni determine digestive efficiency and metabolism in Ayurveda.

Ama

Improper digestion produces Ama, which blocks body channels and weakens immunity. Ama is considered a major cause of many chronic diseases.

Modern parallels include

- Metabolic waste accumulation
- Inflammation
- Gut microbiome imbalance
- Toxin formation
- Poor digestion

Current research on gut health and metabolism strongly supports the importance of proper digestion.

Food Classification in Ayurveda

Ayurveda classifies food according to multiple properties:

According to Rasa

Six tastes are described

- Madhura (sweet)
- Amla (sour)
- Lavana (salty)
- Katu (pungent)
- Tikta (bitter)
- Kashaya (astringent)

Each taste has specific effects on doshas and body tissues.

Personalized Nutrition in Ayurveda (Prakriti-Based Diet)

Ayurveda recommends individualized diet according to body constitution (Prakriti):

Vata Prakriti

Needs warm, oily, nourishing food.

Pitta Prakriti

Needs cooling, sweet, and less spicy food.

Kapha Prakriti

Needs light, dry, and pungent food.

This resembles modern personalized nutrition and nutrigenomics.

According to Guna

Food qualities include

- Guru (heavy)
- Laghu (light)
- Snigdha (unctuous)
- Ruksha (dry)

- Ushna (hot)
- Shita (cold)

These qualities influence digestion and metabolism.

According to Virya

Foods may have

- Ushna Virya (heating effect)
- Shita Virya (cooling effect)

According to Vipaka (Post-digestive Effect)

Vipaka determines the final metabolic effect of food after digestion.

This multidimensional food classification is broader than simple calorie-based modern nutrition.

Ahara and Mental Health

- Ayurveda explains that food affects mental qualities:
- Sattvic food promotes calmness and clarity
- Rajasic food increases restlessness and irritability
- Tamasic food causes laziness and dullness

Modern nutritional psychiatry also studies the relationship between diet, mood, anxiety, and depression through the gut-brain axis.

Ritucharya: Seasonal Dietary

Ayurveda advises changing food habits according to seasons:

Winter

Heavy and nourishing foods are recommended.

Summer

Cooling and light foods should be consumed.

Rainy Season

Warm and easily digestible foods are advised.

Modern science also recognizes seasonal changes in metabolism and immunity.

Dinacharya and Meal Timing

Ayurveda emphasizes proper meal timing. Midday is considered the best time for the main meal because digestive fire is strongest at that time.

Late-night heavy meals are discouraged.

Modern chrononutrition research also supports meal timing and circadian rhythm for metabolic health.

Modern Relevance of Ahara Vidhi Vidhan

Many Ayurvedic dietary principles now correlate with modern scientific findings:

Ayurvedic Concept	Modern Correlation
Agni	Metabolism and digestive enzymes
Ama	Inflammation and toxins
Ritucharya	Seasonal nutrition
Dinacharya	Circadian biology
Prakriti	Personalized nutrition
Pathya Ahara	Functional foods
Mindful eating	Behavioural nutrition

Thus, Ayurveda offers a holistic and preventive nutritional framework.

DISCUSSION

Modern lifestyle habits such as fast-food consumption, stress, lack of sleep, overeating, and irregular meal timing are major causes of lifestyle diseases. Ayurveda had already warned against these faulty dietary habits.

The principles of Ahara Vidhi Vidhan are practical and scientifically relevant because they focus on

- Proper digestion
- Fresh food
- Balanced quantity
- Healthy combinations
- Mental relaxation
- Individualized diet

One of the most important Ayurvedic concepts is that digestion is more important than simply eating nutritious food. Even healthy food can produce disease if digestion is weak.

Modern studies on gut microbiome, inflammatory disorders, metabolism, and circadian rhythm increasingly support these classical Ayurvedic ideas.

CONCLUSION

Ahara Vidhi Vidhan provides a comprehensive and holistic dietary framework for maintaining health and preventing disease. Ayurveda explains not only what should be eaten but also how, when, where, and in what quantity food should be consumed.

These principles strongly resemble modern concepts of preventive medicine, mindful eating, gut health, personalized nutrition, and lifestyle management.

In today's era of increasing lifestyle disorders, the Ayurvedic approach toward food can provide safe, practical, and sustainable guidance for healthy living. By combining classical Ayurvedic wisdom with modern scientific research, Ahara Vidhi Vidhan can contribute significantly to future nutritional science and global health.

REFERENCES

1. Ghanekara BG. Vaidyakiya Subhasita Sahityam. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Prakashan; 2011.
2. Murthy KRS, editor. Susruta Samhita. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2012.
3. Trikamji Y, editor. Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Dipika Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2017.
4. Murthy KRS, editor. Sarangadhara Samhita. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2016.
5. Paradakara HSS, editor. Astanga Hridayam. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2002.
6. Sharma RK, Dash B. Agnivesa's Charaka Samhita. Vol. 2. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Series Office; 2011.
7. Food and Agriculture Organization. Why we need to eat well. In: Family Nutrition Guide [Internet]. 2004 [cited 2026 May 29]. Available from: <http://www.fao.org/3/y5740e/y5740e04.htm>
8. Bulusu S, editor. Ashtanga Hridayam. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2008.
9. Sastri B, editor. Yogaratnakara. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Prakashan; 2015.
10. Chordia S. Evaluation of the effect of Ahara Vidhi Vidhana in Annavaha and Purisavaha Srotogata Vyadhis with special reference to Tanmana Bhunjita basic principle. Jamnagar: IPGT&R; 2002.
11. Times Food. Reasons why eating while standing is a bad habit [Internet]. 2018 [cited 2026 May 29]. Available from: <https://recipes.timesofindia.com/articles/health/reasons-why-eating-while-standing-is-a-bad-habit/photostory/65489773.cms>

12. Shastri AD, editor. Sushruta Samhita with Nibandha Sangraha Commentary. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 2012.
13. Sukla A. Ayurveda: The science of healthy living. Delhi: Prathibha Prakashan; 2017.
14. Panda AK, Kar S. Viruddhahara and its modern perspective. *Int J Res Ayurveda Pharm.*, 2016; 7(6): 66-70.
15. Trikamji Y, editor. Charaka Samhita. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; 2011.
16. Zope SA, Zope RA. Diet and lifestyle for prevention of non-communicable diseases: Ayurveda perspective. *J Ethnopharmacol.*, 2020; 250: 112489.
17. Tripathi YB. Ayurveda and modern nutrition science: Converging paradigms. *Curr Sci.* 2014; 107(11): 1800-4.
18. Sharma PV, editor. Charaka Samhita. English translation. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia; 2014.
19. Sharma R, Dash B. Agnivesha's Charaka Samhita: Text with English translation. New Delhi: Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan; 2015.
20. Tiwari P. Ayurveda and dietetics: A holistic approach. *J Ayurveda Integr Med.*, 2019; 10(3): 194-200.
21. Sharma H, Chandola HM. Ayurvedic concepts of diet and nutrition. *Ayu.*, 2011; 32(4): 467-71.
22. Rastogi S. Translational Ayurveda: Diet and nutrition. *Anc. Sci. Life.*, 2018; 37(4): 191-8.
23. Chatterjee S, Variyar P. Nutraceuticals and Ayurveda: Evidence-based synergy. *Curr. Nutr. Food Sci.*, 2020; 16: 684-91.
24. Deolankar SC. Food and nutrition in Ayurveda. *Indian J Tradit. Knowl.*, 2003; 2(1): 53-8.
25. Gupta K, Sharma S. Ayurvedic dietary regimen and gut microbiome. *J Integr. Med.*, 2021; 19(4): 295-302.
26. Singh RH. Exploring principles of dietetics in Ayurveda. *Indian J Hist. Sci.*, 2015; 50: 165-74.
27. World Health Organization. Diet, nutrition and the prevention of chronic diseases. WHO Technical Report Series No. 916. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2003.
28. Kalra EK. Nutraceuticals—Definition and introduction. *AAPS Pharm. Sci.*, 2003; 5(3): 27-35.
29. Subramanian M, et al. Chrononutrition: Emerging evidence and relevance to Ayurveda. *Nutr. Rev.*, 2019; 77(12): 853-66.
30. Choudhary A, Singh A. Functional foods in Ayurveda. *Int. J Ayurveda Pharma. Res.*, 2017; 5(7): 25-30.